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Exploitation Plan of the COST Action PurpleGain CA21146

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SUMMARY

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF PURPLE GAIN PROJECT	3
2 PURPOSE	3
3 PROCESS	4
4 EXPLOITATION PLAN- METHODOLOGY	5
5 EXPLOITATION PLAN- ACTIVITIES	7
5.1 KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS	7
5.2 MARKET EVALUATION FOR EXPLOITABLE RESULTS	7
5.3 STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION AND INVOLVEMENT	8
5.4 PROJECT RESULTS MONITORING	9
5.5 CERTIFICATION AND PRODUCTS SECURITY ISSUE	10
6 CASE STUDIES	11
6.1 THE DEMO SCALE PLANT OF LINARES (JAEN, SPAIN)	11
6.2 THE DEMO SCALE PHOTO-MBR OF BRISBANE (QUEENSLAND, AUSTRALIA).....	12
6.3 THE PILOT SCALE OPEN POND PHOTOBIOREACTOR AT IITKHARAGPUR	13

FIGURE and TABLE INDEX

Table 1: Purposes of the Exploitation Plan	3
Table 2: PurpleGain results current state and innovation.....	7
Table 3: PurpleGain results market evaluation and barriers.....	8
Table 4: PurpleGain draft list of potential stakeholders.....	9
Table 5: Legislation and Regulation of PurpleGain products and technologies	10
Figure 1. Relationship between the market growth and market share in the development of a product or a technology.....	5
Figure 1: Step-by-step exploitation methodology for PurpleGain Project	6
Figure 2: The Purple Phototrophic Bacteria (PPB)-based demonstrative photo-bioreactor implemented at the WWTP located in Linares (Jaén Spain).....	12
Figure 3. Schematic representation of the treatment plant, including the photobioreactor.	13

1 Executive summary of PURPLE GAIN Project

PURPLEGAIN aims to create a European network to share information, facilitating technology and knowledge transfer between the academic and industrial sectors, related to Purple Photosynthetic Bacteria (PPB) applications for resource recovery from organic waste sources. Resource recovery includes wastewater or organic waste, open or closed environments, in single or chain processes. PURPLEGAIN also aims to create a database for techno-economic, social, and environmental impacts studies, which facilitates the marketability of both the PPB-based technologies and the products to extract. Some focused products are polyhydroxyalkanoates, single-cell proteins, biomass for energy, biomass as fertilizer, biohydrogen, carotenoids, terpenoids, organic acids, coenzyme Q10, and 5-aminolevulinic acid. The network connects fundamental- and applied- research groups, improving lab-scale technology optimization through mechanistic modelling. It benefits the technology transfer from applied-research groups to industry, considerably improving process design.

2 Purpose

The purpose of this document is to outline strategies for the exploitation of project results both during its implementation and after its conclusion. These strategies are designed to maximize the exploitation of the intellectual outputs and other content developed during the funding period, which are important goals for the PurpleGain implementation. Therefore, this Plan aims to indicate how the consortium will establish the basis for the exploitation activities and it summarizes the concrete steps to be performed in relation to the exploitation of the project outputs.

Table 1: Purposes of the Exploitation Plan

	RESULTS EXPLOITATION
Objectives	Make concrete use of results for research, knowledge transfer or commercial use.
Expected Impact	For socio-economic purposes, further research, market validation, licencing, norms setting, standardisation. Represents society's direct & indirect return on the public sector's investment in research. To equip stakeholders with the knowledge, skills, tools, mechanisms, and attitudes on Purple Photosynthetic Bacteria (PPB) applications via the creation of a DB.
Audiences	In addition to researchers and consortium partners: incubators, venture capital, local, national or EU-related innovation ecosystems including policymakers and regulatory bodies, industry, SMEs, sector of interest, civil society.
Languages	Combines both general and technical language to present reports, results, prototypes, software, data, etc.
Channels & Tools	Stakeholder groups and events, industry publications/reports, competitions/awards. EU related platforms and services such as CORDIS, Horizon Results Booster, Innovation Radar, Horizon Results platform,

European Patent Office.

When needed, exploitation results will be published via social networks (LinkedIn and Twitter)
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3 Process

- In the MoU, the following three types of impacts were defined considering the valorization chain and impact pathway of PurpleGain. **Scientific impacts:** (i) The networking activities between participants with different backgrounds will allow the creation of **harmonized protocols** and define a set of **standard practices**. It will be useful not only for research groups and industries when approaching PPB technologies and products, but also to compare results and performances of different systems; (ii) The action activities will promote **knowledge sharing** and encourage **international collaborations**, which will lead to teams' internationalization and the potential generation of new research projects. In the long term, the action structure and members' contacts will remain and support future collaborations and initiatives; (iii) **Young researchers, Ph.D. students, and industry professionals** (technicians, engineers) will participate in conferences, short term scientific missions, workshops, training activities, obtaining **new skillset** in the proposed topics that will be used for the technology expansion. The availability of skilled young researchers, engineers and technicians and support of careers structure for young professionals will increase the scientific innovation capacity in Europe in the field of PPB biotechnology and beyond.
- **Techno-economic impacts:** (i) The Action will propose **new technical solutions** to overcome current process and product sustainability challenges, namely the expected significant breakthroughs on light delivery systems, on microbial culture operational practices fitted to each case scenario (e.g., type of waste stream, regional conditions), and on new methodologies for efficient resource recovery (both material and energetic) and products extraction; (ii) The technological development will impact **companies associated to the PPB sector along the entire value chain** from upstream to downstream companies (photobioreactors builders, sensors, analytical and processing equipment, products quality control and commercialization); (iii) The Action will promote **cross-sector collaborations** between waste treatment companies, waste producers and bioproducts companies for the effective implementation of PPB technology.
- **Societal impacts:** (i) PurpleGain is an action that promotes a **sustainable technology** focused on **resource recovery and waste valorization**. This technology addresses societal pressing concerns on resource scarcity, pollution, and renewable energy and introduces PPB technology for its ability to contribute to the emerging negative emissions discourse. In the long term, PPB technological implementation will directly benefit the environment and contribute to society through **public health protection**, for example through the reduction of synthetic compounds use. (ii) New **bioproducts** (bioplastics, fertilizers, food, and cosmetics, supplements) will be produced and commercialized, becoming available to society and answering the public demand for eco-friendly and sustainable products. (iii) Through the dissemination activities to the general public, society will be alerted to the necessity of a **circular economy** and informed on how implementing sustainable processes and using bioproducts can step-wisely move society to a greener economy.

Over the project implementation this document will be continuously revised and improved based on the achieved results, to ensure the best exploitation strategy and the highest impact. To carry out the regular review and update of this document, consortium partners will use the Project Core Group meetings and feedback from evaluation activities to respond to any need for adjustment through the development of new strategies to increase project impact.

4 Exploitation Plan- Methodology

PurpleGain's exploitation plan is closely linked to dissemination activities due to the type and nature of the expected results. Exploitation of the results depends indeed on the partnership's ability to create a strong network among stakeholders to make long- term use of the scientific advancement and strategies developed supporting the policy development and adoption of the results. The Plan is therefore aligned with the dissemination strategy and will be continuously monitored and possibly revised and improved.

Results of the Action will not only impact on scientists researching on the different disciplines involved in the Action (biologist, chemists, biotechnologists, engineers...) but also on European policy makers who in view of the results will be able to launch new initiatives to further reduce Europe dependence on fossil fuels, plastics, synthetic plant fertilizers and stimulants among many other utilities. Exploitation of results will be preferentially performed by companies dealing with the design, construction, and management of PPB biobased processes.

This COST Action deals with the use of PPB for bioproducts with potential economic, environmental, and societal benefits. From this point of view, results of the Action are expected to have far-reaching outcomes at both industrial and societal benefits. Those benefits do not only concern the sustainable energy sector, but positive effects will also be observed in many other industry segments, such as agriculture, cosmetics, bioplastics, and chemical industry.

Through interaction between scientists and other stakeholders as well as identification of new stakeholders, existing markets could be developed, or new markets with high growth potential could be explored (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Relationship between the market growth and market share in the development of a product or a technology.

Considering the nature of the Cost Action, the step-by-step methodology could help the consortium to reach a common Exploitation Plan at the end of the project. The steps and the related activities are listed below and detailed in the following paragraph:

- 1 – Identification of the key exploitable results.
- 2- Market evaluation for exploitable results.
- 3- Stakeholder identification and involvement.
- 4- Project results monitoring.
- 5- Certification and product security issues.
- 6- Define the monetization routes for project results
- 7- Preparation of a shared exploitation roadmaps

Figure 1: Step-by-step exploitation methodology for PurpleGain Project

The relationships with industry networks, policymakers, and higher education institutions should be maintained and strengthened during the project implementation so that they can contribute, to the dissemination of PurpleGain policies even beyond the end of the project e.g., by collaborating on the organization and dissemination of thematic webinars after the end of the activities.

5 Exploitation Plan- Activities

5.1 Key exploitable results

The first step is to preliminary identify the pool of key exploitable results generated in the development of the technical WPs by creating a state of the art of products and technologies development (Table 2).

A list of innovations derived from the PurpleGain Cost Action, including new products, protocols, technological patents, and start-ups, will be published yearly, including the economic and social impacts of the innovations, as well as the forecast for the exploitation activities (including start-ups). Table 2 shows an example of the current state of the art of both technologies and products, where the third column will be actualized yearly with the advancements achieved or promoted by PurpleGain.

Table 2: PurpleGain results current state and innovation

PRODUCTS	State of the Art/ current state of development	Purple Gain Innovation
Bioplastics	Pilot scale (TRL 6)	
Biofertilizers	Demonstrative scale (TRL 7)	
Biostimulants	Lab scale (TRL 3)	
Proteins	Lab scale (TRL 3)	
Clean water	Demonstrative scale (TRL 8)	
TECHNOLOGIES	State of the Art/ current state of development	Purple Gain Innovation
Anaerobic raceway pond	Demonstrative scale (TRL 8)	
Flat-plate Photo-MBR	Pilot scale (TRL 6)	
Tubular photobioreactor	Lab scale (TRL 3)	
Chemostat photobioreactor	Lab scale (TRL 3)	
Photo-bioelectrochemical reactor	Lab scale (TRL 3)	

5.2 Market evaluation for exploitable results

The analysis on Purple Gain products and technologies marketability, could reveal specific barriers that slow down the commercialization. Market evaluation will be made by considering European cases but with a look at Global situations related to sustainability impact (society, economy, environment). To improve the knowledge about the issues -marketability and barriers- the dialogue with stakeholders is fundamental.

Table 3: PurpleGain results market evaluation and barriers

PRODUCTS	Market evaluation	Barriers
Bioplastics	Packaging, materials, surgery	Complex HA's mixtures make difficult to find real applications due to heterogeneity.
Biofertilizers	Soil and plant fertilization	Poor pelletization of biomass hinders marketability
Biostimulants	Agriculture, wasteland recovery	Purity of the mix. Potential biodegradability of the biostimulant. Purification is expensive.
Microbial protein for food/feed	Food industry	Lack of accepted PPB species on EFSA list
Clean water (WWT)	Wastewater	Poor biomass settleability, low nutrients removal capacity
TECHNOLOGIES	Market evaluation	
Anaerobic raceway pond	Wastewater, waste streams	Already developed (TRL 8)
Flat-plate Photo-MBR	Wastewater, waste streams	High land use, poor volume/surface ratio
Tubular photobioreactor	Wastewater, biotechnology, food industry	Lack of efficient materials for natural illumination, poor biomass harvesting
Chemostat photobioreactor	Biotechnology, food industry, pharmacy industry, bioplastics industry, hydrogen industry	High illumination costs, poor biomass harvesting
Photo-bioelectrochemical reactor	Energy, Wastewater, food industry	Poor volume/surface ratio, high materials costs

5.3 Stakeholder identification and involvement

Third step is about the identification of stakeholders and of effective channels to engage potential users, such as specific stakeholder networks and platforms, project website and social channels. A stakeholder coordinator (SC) has been nominated and will supervise the efficiency of the procedure.

The stakeholder feedback on the project idea is essential to modulate the product/technology development according to the users' requirements. During the PurpleGain Project specific roundtables and meetings will be organised for joint exploitation initiatives. The dissemination and communication manager will chair the meetings to ensure compliance with the PurpleGain mission and policies.

The exploitation activities defined by the consortium and developed during the project include the following use of: **partners' platform for sharing the outputs of the project; partners' exploitation channels; offline events to present the outputs** (See the dissemination plan)

Table 4: PurpleGain draft list of potential stakeholders

Sectors	Leading technologies Companies/Associations/Institutions	Member State
Bioplastics	European Bioplastic Association	EU-all
	The Biodegradable Plastics Association	(UK)
	Assobioplastiche	IT
	Aimplas	ES
	Novamont	IT
	Arkema	FR
	BASF	GE
Biofertilizers	Eurochem Group	SW
	Fertinagro Biotech	SP
	Tradecorp	SP
	European Consortium of Organic Plant Breeders (ECO-PB)	EU-all
	European Sustainable Phosphorus Platform (ESPP)	EU-all
	Groupe Roullier	FR
	Biostimulants	The European Biostimulant Industry Council (EBIC)
Valagro		IT
Wastewater Treatment	Aqualia	ES
	Veolia Water	FR
	Suez Environment	FR
	The International Water Association	UK
	Thames Water	UK
	ACEA	IT
	Acciona	ES
	Seven Trent	UK
	SAUR	FR
EYDAP	EL	

5.4 Project results monitoring

PurpleGain is directly in line with a) the EC “Innovation Radar” which aims at identifying and supporting high potential exploitable results, to represent a pathway to enacting, measuring and accelerating commercial and economic outputs and b) with retaining competitive IP advantages within EU. The PurpleGain results monitoring process will be a continuous process of collecting and analysing information to compare how the project objectives are being implemented against market development and policy requirements.

5.5 Certification and products security issue

Some of the barriers are related to certification and product security. An update of the current legislation/regulation will help the identification of these issues and to develop a strategy for policy makers, to improve the PPB utilisation.

This evaluation process will be performed for each type of product and technology studied and developed during PurpleGain.

Table 5: Legislation and Regulation of PurpleGain products and technologies

PRODUCTS	Regulation	Barriers
Bioplastics	Waste Framework Directive (revision) Packaging and Packaging Waste (revision)	Still unclear the preferable end-of-life treatment – small market inhibits centralized recycling Lack of legislative framework for bio-based plastics There are multiple overlapping schemes for the certification of bioproducts. Certification is expensive, time consuming and requires significant expertise
Biofertilizers	Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 – laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products Commission Regulation (EC) No 889/2008 of 5 September 2008 laying down detailed rules for the implementation of Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007 on organic production and labelling of organic products with regard to organic production, labelling and control. Fertilizers Regulation (EU) 2019/1009:	Regulatory and policy constraints, regulatory framework is complex and varies, obtaining necessary permits is resource intensive Ensuring consistent quality and performance can be challenging – robust quality control measures are needed Building trust and acceptance with end-users and consumers
Biostimulants	<u>REACH Regulation (EC 1907/2006)</u>	Regulation and guidelines for production is missing
Proteins	Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009 on Animal By-products Regulation (EU) No 2015/2283	Quality and safety concerns related to contamination of final products with metals, antibiotics resistant genes and

	on Novel Foods:	bacteria, pathogenic bacteria, RNA and DNA, and hazardous organic compounds.
Clean water (WWT)	Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse (Text with EEA relevance)	Potential pathogens concentration in the effluents
TECHNOLOGIES	Regulation	
Anaerobic raceway pond	Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (UWWTD) (Council Directive 91/271/EEC)	No detected barriers (currently commercialized)
Flat-plate Photo-MBR		Safety concerns if used for feed/food production
Tubular photobioreactor		Safety concerns if used for feed/food production
Chemostat photobioreactor		Technological barriers related to artificial illumination
Photo-bioelectrochemical reactor		Technological barriers related to materials costs and production (e.g., electrodes)

6 Case studies

6.1 The demo scale plant of Linares (Jaen, Spain)

The implementation of the DEEP PURPLE biorefinery concept in the demo scale plant of Linares (Spain) is an example of PPB technology development within a wastewater treatment plant (WWTP). The Purple Phototrophic Bacteria (PPB) has been implemented at the WWTP located in Linares (Jaén Spain) (Figure 2); the plant is operated by Aqualia and owned by Linares Council. This plant uses conventional activated sludge technology and has a treatment capacity of 15,000 m³/d. In this demo plant, two twin anaerobic photobioreactors has been implemented for treating up to 350 m³/d of municipal wastewater to produce enriched PPB biomass (Biomass Platform) as feedstock for production of slow-release fertilizers. Treated water complies with discharge limits for COD, TSS and BDO₅.

Figure 2: The Purple Phototrophic Bacteria (PPB)-based demonstrative photo-bioreactor implemented at the WWTP located in Linares (Jaén Spain)

6.2 The demo scale photo-MBR of Brisbane (Queensland, Australia)

The demonstration plant consisted of a flat plate photobioreactor of 1 m³ (10 m long), covered with UV/VIS absorbing foil (Figure 3). This was the first demonstration scale PPB-based photobioreactor in operation. It has been installed in a cattle farm to treat wastewater and produce microbial protein. The system can treat around 0.5 m³ per day for long periods of time under natural irradiation.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the treatment plant, including the photobioreactor.

6.3 The pilot scale open pond photobioreactor at IITKharagpur

Within the framework of the Saraswati 2.0 EU-India programme 10 decentralized wastewater treatment systems are piloted in India. One of these concerns two stage CSTR acidifying fermenter followed by a raceway PPB reactor. Although stage 1 has a capacity of 100m³/day, only 1m³/d is directed to a 10m² raceway PPB reactor treating municipal sewage at the campus of IITKharagpur. The pilot has been designed in collaboration with TUDelft and UAntwerp, and has been operational since beginning of 2023, due to delay caused by the COVID crisis. Ultimate aim of the pilot is to test the PPB technology for rural settings and enable the operation by less skilled operators through advancing on control engineering. Non-edible PPB products are explored for their potential in the Indian market.